

Intraocular Pressure (IOP) and Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer Thickness (RNFL) Association in Patients with PseudoexfoliationWalad P.J¹, Manekar A.V.², Mohod P.N.³¹Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Dr. Panjabrao Alias Bhausaheb Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati²Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Dr. Panjabrao Alias Bhausaheb Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Dr. Panjabrao Alias Bhausaheb Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati

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Abstract:

Background: Pseudoexfoliation syndrome (PXF) is an age-related condition marked by the accumulation of fibrillar extracellular material in the eye, often leading to secondary open-angle glaucoma. This accumulation increases aqueous humor outflow resistance, raising intraocular pressure (IOP), a key risk factor for optic nerve damage. Additionally, retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thinning is an important indicator of glaucomatous damage, influenced by both IOP and pressure-independent factors. Thus, this study aims to assess the relationship between IOP and RNFL thickness in patients with PXF.

Materials and method: This cross-sectional study was conducted at a tertiary healthcare center from November 2022 to April 2024, enrolling 112 patients (180 eyes) with pseudoexfoliation material. The inclusion criteria for the study required the presence of pseudoexfoliation material on either the pupillary margin or the lens capsule. Patients were excluded if they had media opacities, were using anti-glaucoma medications, had undergone prior ocular surgeries, or had other ocular disorders. Comprehensive ocular examinations, including visual acuity, slit lamp biomicroscopy, gonioscopy, IOP measurement, and optical coherence tomography (OCT) for RNFL assessment, were performed. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: This study found a majority of participants (44.64%) in the 61-70 years age group, with a female predominance (59.82%). Bilateral pseudoexfoliation was more common (60.71%). Most cases (36.66%) exhibited IOP levels in the 21-25 mmHg range, while 63.34% showed RNFL thinning. A significant correlation was observed between RNFL thinning and IOP status, with 26.62% of thinning cases presenting with elevated IOP.

Conclusion: The findings highlight significant associations between elevated IOP and RNFL thinning in patients with pseudoexfoliation. Early detection and monitoring are crucial for preventing potential visual impairment in this population.

Keywords: Intraocular Pressure, Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer Thickness, Pseudoexfoliation.

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Introduction

Pseudoexfoliation (PXF) is a leading cause of secondary open-angle glaucoma. The risk of developing PXF is significantly increased by mutations in the LOXL1 gene located at locus 15q24, which is responsible for coding elastic fibers in the extracellular matrix. This condition is characterized by the production of a gray-white fibrillary extracellular material.

This material consists of a protein core surrounded by glycosaminoglycans and results from the abnormal basement membranes of aging epithelial cells. [1] It can be found in various structures, including the trabeculum, equatorial lens capsule,

iris, and ciliary body. This material is deposited on the anterior lens capsule, zonules, ciliary body, iris, trabeculum, anterior vitreous face, and optic nerve head. [2] Pseudoexfoliation syndrome (PXS) is a systemic disorder of the extracellular matrix characterized by the deposition of extracellular fibrillary material in ocular tissues, skin, and other visceral organs.

This condition can lead to various cardiovascular and cerebrovascular abnormalities, as well as hearing loss. Approximately 50% of patients with PXS may progress to develop pseudoexfoliation glaucoma (PXG). [3] In patients with PXF, the

accumulation of pseudoexfoliative material in the trabecular meshwork increases resistance to aqueous humor outflow, resulting in elevated intraocular pressure (IOP). This elevation is a key risk factor for glaucomatous optic neuropathy and visual field defects, which are defining features of PXG. [4]

Additionally, retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness is an essential marker of optic nerve integrity, where thinning signifies glaucomatous damage. [5] While elevated IOP is a major risk factor for optic nerve damage, various pressure-independent factors have also been identified as contributors to RNFL loss, including decreased ocular and retrobulbar perfusion, abnormalities in lamina cribrosa elastic tissues, and the accumulation of exfoliative material in the trabecular meshwork. [6]

Understanding these factors may help in developing targeted therapies and enhancing early detection of damage in patients with PXF, allowing for timely interventions to prevent further optic nerve damage and visual field loss. Therefore, this study aims to assess the relationship between RNFL thickness and IOP in PXF patients.

Materials and Method

This cross sectional study was conducted at a tertiary health care from November 2022 to April 2024. A total of 112 patients including 180 eyes were enrolled in the study after obtaining written informed consent.

Patients exhibiting the presence of pseudoexfoliation material on the pupillary margin or lens capsule, who also provided consent to participate in the research were included in the study.

Patients with media opacity that interfered with the visualization and capturing of OCT images, as well as those already on antiglaucoma medications were not included in the study. Additionally, individuals who had previously undergone cataract, glaucoma, or refractive surgery were excluded. Patients with ocular surface disorders, ocular infections such as corneal ulcers and infectious keratitis, ocular inflammation, and any retinal disorders were not

enrolled in the study. The study was conducted by the Declaration of Helsinki. Institutional Ethical committee approval was obtained. Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants before their inclusion in the study.

Patients who fulfilled inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study. Detailed history regarding ocular symptoms and systemic complaints was taken. A general systemic examination was done to rule out systemic illness. In ocular examination, visual acuity was recorded. Anterior segment evaluation was done with a slit lamp biomicroscope. Intra-ocular pressure was recorded using an application tonometer during office hours. Gonioscopy was done using 4 mirror gonioscope. The optic disc was evaluated using a direct ophthalmoscope and 78 D Lens. Posterior segment examination was carried out using both 90D and indirect ophthalmoscopy. Central corneal thickness was measured with a Pachymeter to calculate the corrected IOP. RNFL thickness was calculated using OCT. Intraocular pressure was categorized into 5 groups: 11-15, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, 31-35 and RNFL thickness was measured and categorized as normal and thinning. The data was entered using Microsoft Excel 2019. The data was analyzed using SPSS 0.6. Descriptive statistics including mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables such as IOP and RNFL. The chi-square test was applied to determine the association between IOP and RNFL thickness. P value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The majority of patients (44.64%) in the 61-70 years group, while the smallest proportion (0.89%) was in the 81-90 years group. Other notable distributions included 25% of cases in the 51-60 years group and 27.67% in the 71-80 years group. The Females accounted for 59.82% of the cases (67 out of 112), while males represented 40.18% (45 out of 112).

The bilateral cases comprising 60.71% (68 out of 112), while unilateral cases accounted for 39.29% (44 out of 112).

Table 1: Distribution of IOP findings

IOP	No. of Cases	Percentage
15-19	60	33.33%
16-20	52	28.88%
21-25	66	36.66%
26-30	1	0.55%
31-35	1	0.55%
Total	180	100%

The above table showed that the majority of cases were in the 21-25 mmHg range, accounting for

36.66% (66 out of 180). This was followed by 15-19 mmHg at 33.33% (60 cases) and 16-20 mmHg

at 28.88% (52 cases). Only a small proportion of cases fell within the 26-30 mmHg and 31-35

mmHg ranges each representing 0.55% (1 case each).

Table 2: RNFL findings in eyes with pseudoexfoliation (n=180)

RNFL findings	Number of Cases	Percentage
Thinning	114	63.34%
Normal	66	36.66%
Total	180	100

The above table showed that the majority thinning, comprising 63.34% (114 out of 180), while normal RNFL findings were observed in 36.66% (66 cases).

Table 3: Association of RNFL and IOL findings in eyes with pseudoexfoliation.

RNFL	IOP Raised		IOP Normal		TOTAL	
	No. of Cases	Percentage	No. of Cases	Percentage	No. of Cases	Percentage
Thinning	47	26.62%	67	37.22%	114	63.33%
Normal	21	11.38%	45	25.00%	66	36.67%
TOTAL	68	37.78%	112	62.22%	180	100%

The above table showed that the thinning RNFL, 47 (26.62%) had raised IOP, while 67 (37.22%) had normal IOP, totalling 114 cases of thinning. For normal RNFL findings, 21 cases (11.38%) had raised IOP, and 45 cases (25.00%) had normal IOP, totalling 66 cases. Overall, there were 68 cases (37.78%) with raised IOP and 112 cases (62.22%) with normal IOP out of 180 total cases.

Discussion

In this study, we examined the relationship between intraocular pressure and retinal nerve fibre layer thickness in patients with pseudoexfoliation syndrome, providing valuable insights into the pathophysiology of glaucomatous optic neuropathy and other ocular conditions.

In the present study, it was observed that the majority of cases (44.64%) occurred in the 61-70 age groups, while the smallest proportion (0.89%) was in the 81-90 age groups. Other significant distributions included 25% of cases in the 51-60 age group and 27.67% in the 71-80 age group. These findings are consistent with the study by Jonasson et al., [7] and Melese et al., [8]

Our study demonstrated a female predominance, with 67 (59.52%) of the 112 cases being female and 45 (40.18%) being male. This aligns with findings from studies like the Framingham Eye Study, which reported a higher prevalence of pseudoexfoliation (PXF) in women, with a female-to-male ratio of 2.3:1. However, other studies, such as those by Aravind et al., [9] Yasmeen et al., [10] and Melese et al., [8] show variations from present study findings.

In the current study, 68 cases (60.71%) of PXF were bilateral, while 44 cases (39.29%) were unilateral. This finding aligns with the Reykjavik Eye Study, where approximately 50% of PXF cases were bilateral. Similarly, Rao et al., [11] observed

that all PXF cases in their study were bilateral. Junejo et al., [12] also reported that PXF can present either unilaterally or bilaterally, with a tendency for unilateral cases to eventually progress to bilateral involvement.

The present study found that the majority of cases exhibited intraocular pressure (IOP) within the 21-25 mmHg range, accounting for 36.66% (66 out of 180 cases). This was followed by the 15-19 mmHg range at 33.33% (60 cases) and the 16-20 mmHg range at 28.88% (52 cases). Only a small proportion of cases were recorded in the 26-30 mmHg and 31-35 mmHg ranges each representing 0.55% (1 case each).

In contrast, the study by Aravind et al., [13] reported that 16.7% of pseudoexfoliation (PXF) patients had elevated IOP (>21 mmHg), 14.8% had occludable angles, and 13% had pseudoexfoliation glaucoma. Rao et al., [11] found that 40% of PXF patients experienced elevated IOP, while the Reykjavik Eye Study highlighted a significant association between PXF and elevated IOP, which predisposes patients to glaucoma development.

The present study revealed that the majority of participants exhibited retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thinning, with 63.34% (114 out of 180) demonstrating this condition, while 36.66% (66 cases) had normal RNFL findings.

Yuksel et al., [14] reported significant RNFL thinning in pseudoexfoliation (PXF) eyes across most quadrants, except for the nasal quadrant, with particular emphasis on certain clock-hour positions. In the unaffected fellow eyes, only the temporal quadrant displayed a significant difference when compared to controls, with minimal differences noted at the 11 o'clock position. Additionally, the RNFL was significantly thinner in the inferior quadrant and specific clock-hour positions of PXF eyes relative to non-PXF eyes. Similarly, a study

by Mohamed et al., [15] found that RNFL thinning was present in all quadrants except the nasal quadrant in PXF patients compared to healthy controls.

The present study also showed that the thinning RNFL, 47 (26.62%) had raised IOP, while 67 (37.22%) had normal IOP, totalling 114 cases of thinning. For normal RNFL findings, 21 cases (11.38%) had raised IOP, and 45 cases (25.00%) had normal IOP, totalling 66 cases. Overall, there were 68 cases (37.78%) with raised IOP and 112 cases (62.22%) with normal IOP out of 180 total cases.

Conclusion

The present study evaluated the association between RNFL thickness and IOP, in participants with pseudoexfoliation. There was a statistically significant correlation between RNFL thickness and IOP ($p = 0.02$).

In our study, 67 eyes (59.82%) had RNFL thinning with normal IOP. Significant RNFL thinning was present even in the absence of raised IOP, emphasizing the role of various pressure-independent factors leading to RNFL thinning in pseudoexfoliation.

It underscores the importance of incorporating RNFL thickness assessment into routine examination of pseudoexfoliation cases aiding early diagnosis of glaucoma and thereby improving visual outcome.

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